

Hotter than hell: understanding highly-irradiated worlds through transmission spectroscopy

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Since the discovery of an exoplanet around a sun-like star in the mid-nineties [1], the field of exoplanet science has made large strides towards a better understanding of planetary atmospheres. First observations from space [2], which were then later confirmed from the ground [3], have since been joined by a plethora of observations of these far away atmospheres. One of the most puzzling results from this early phase of discoveries are hot and ultra hot Jupiters, the latter being Jupiter-sized planets with temperatures above 2000 K. These worlds have no equivalent in our Solar System and provide insights into the most extreme conditions atmospheres can be placed under.

Transmission spectroscopy

To study these enigmatic highly irradiated atmospheres, one can utilise the so called transmission spectroscopy method, where the planet is observed while it occults part of the starlight captured by the observer. During this occultation part of the light is not blocked but interacts with the atmosphere of the exoplanet as it traverses. Depending on which particles the light encounters in the atmosphere, it is then absorbed, changing the apparent radius of the planet depending on the absorption wavelength. The detection of this atmospheric absorption gives us information about the composition of the atmosphere, but the depth of the absorption line is also directly proportional to the absorption height in the atmosphere (see Figure 1). This allows us to create a vertical profile of the observed exoplanet atmosphere.

Figure 1: Depiction of an exoplanet transit in front of a host star. The lower panel shows the absorption as a function of time, called a lightcurve.

Studying winds in ultra hot Jupiters

One of the various subfields of interest to paint a more coherent picture of exoplanet atmospheres is the study of their wind profiles and, in the case of highly irradiated planets such as hot Jupiters, their mass loss. From observations of phase curves in the infra-red and subsequent modelling with global circulation models (so called GCMs, see [4]), we know that most giant gas planets have a zonal structure up to the millibar level in pressure with winds either super-rotating faster than the planet itself or, for tidally locked hot Jupiters, a day to night side wind, blowing from the hot, constantly irradiated day side to the cooler night side (see, e.g. [5] for HD189733 b).

On the other hand, from observations of the main constituents of hot Jupiter atmospheres, Hydrogen and Helium, in the ultra violet we can study the outermost rim of these atmospheres. For example [6] studied the hot Jupiter HD189733 b with the Hubble Space Telescope to observe its Lyman- α absorption and found that even long after the planet had already left the stellar disk it had occulted before, the atmosphere continued to obscure part of the star. This result led to the conclusion that the exoplanet is blasted with stellar irradiation and the outer layer of its atmosphere (at the nanobar level in pressure) evaporates material into space, dragging a comet-like tail behind the planet.

But how are these horizontal winds at the millibar level connected to the mass loss in the outermost parts of the atmosphere? This question is answered for the specific case of the ultra hot Jupiter WASP-76 b in my work on the connecting layers between the above described pressure regimes, which we will call here the intermediate atmosphere.

The intermediate atmosphere and radial winds

Transmission spectroscopy has one compelling advantage when conducted from the ground: the spectral absorption lines from the atmosphere can be resolved in wavelength, so called high-resolution transmission spectroscopy. And one of the best targets for this kind of observation is the sodium doublet in the yellow visible wavelength range. Due to its large oscillator strength, this resonant doublet produces a large absorption feature even if only a small fraction of sodium is present in the atmosphere. In consequence, the shape of the sodium absorption feature traces through the entire atmosphere of the exoplanet up the thermosphere, thus bridging the two wind regimes discussed before.

In [7], this knowledge of the line shape was exploited via a nested sampling retrieval algorithm that compared

Figure 2: Figure 5 from Seidel [9]. The combined data of three HARPS and two ESPRESSO transits of WASP-76 b is shown with the best fit model in blue and a model solely with lower atmospheric day to night side wind in orange.

a theoretical line shape broadened via the Doppler-effect from different atmospheric wind patterns with the observed line shape for the hot Jupiter HD189733 b. This code is called MERC in the following. Already in this work, we found that the line shape can only be explained by a radial, vertical wind. However, some simplifications were made to save computing time, meaning that the wind speed had to be considered an upper limit.

In the follow up work presented in the Hypatia series, these simplifications were removed and a latitude dependence of the winds introduced, so that the poles and the equator had physically sound differences in wind speed. Additionally, planetary rotation was accounted for. This update of MERC was then applied to the ultra hot Jupiter WASP-76 b (see Figure 2), and revealed a day to night side wind of roughly 5 km s^{-1} in the lower atmosphere at the millibar level and at higher pressures. This observational retrieval result is compatible with the same wind pattern and speed found for this planet in [8], where iron was traced in time during the transit. In the intermediate atmosphere the same radial, vertical wind connects the

zonal winds in the lower atmosphere with the expanding atmosphere in the outer layers that was already found for HD189733 b. This vertical wind is likely driven by the strong irradiation which is also responsible for the upper atmospheric mass loss. An additional hypothesis is the possible interaction of ions in the zonal winds with the strong magnetic field of these ultra hot planets. These findings were subsequently published in [9].

Additional studies of other ultra hot Jupiters are necessary to verify the origin and strength of this wind in WASP-76 b and to understand if this vertical wind is a common feature in highly irradiated atmospheres.

References

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